

The Influence of Mass Media on the Consciousness of the Young Generation, Psychological Problems and Solutions

Razikova L.T.

*Samarkand State medical university,
Departments Associate Professor
of Pedagogy and Psychology*

Abstract

In this article, the problem of information and psychological security arises historically with the formation of any state and social, political, economic interests in society and their expression in the ideological sphere. Already, from this time, together with stability and development, informational and psychological dangers and spiritual threats of a certain nature appear. This article explains the concept of information security and its essence

Keywords: *information, information-psychological security, civilization, information crisis, destructive idea, information sector, sub consciousness, unconsciousness, emotional state.*

Introduction

The concept of information is gaining global importance today. Because it has become a powerful weapon that affects our thinking in different directions, turns life and thousands of destinies in it in one direction or another, sometimes acquires a negative, sometimes positive essence. In general, information is a reflection of the objects of the material world that are reflected in an organism or a group of organisms and are used by them to adapt to environmental changes. A word that once acquired a divine meaning, its power has reached today to decide the fate of the world. has risen to the status of a powerful tool that plays the main role in After the scientific and technical revolution, the high-speed development of communication technologies and information infrastructures, in particular, the emergence of the Internet and its deep penetration into the way of social life in a short period of time, turned information into the most expensive product. In fact, in the conditions of globalization and integration, information, which has more value than gold, platinum, jewels, has taken its place in the world market. Whoever owns the information rules the world, and it is not for nothing that his ideas are widely remembered.

4-5 centuries ago, the number of troops, the arsenal of weapons, even the ships in the sea, and the military potential in general, were of great importance for leading the world.

In fact, the concept of information has long existed in the field of all knowledge representing the worldview. The emergence of a fully informed global system has closely linked the fate of nations, peoples and the whole of humanity. On the other hand, it should be noted that the unimaginable development of the technology of obtaining, processing, storing and distributing information is a serious concern today. After all, the latest generation of computers can perform up to two billion tasks every second. Thanks to such a miracle of information technology, a person can establish contact with a person at any point of the earth in seconds, find answers to questions that interest him instantly. This situation itself expresses the human activity, way of thinking, moral standards, relations with the world, as a whole, the life and destiny of humanity in the new century. In other words, the civilization of the 21st century is manifesting itself in the form of an information crisis, an information-psychological war.

Every citizen acts only within the framework of his personal point of view, views, spiritual-educational, moral and spiritual capabilities. He lives in the territory of his world and reacts to the outside world within the limits of his mind. Each individual, as an independent person, receives and analyzes information suitable for him based on his natural and biological maturity and spiritual needs. Based on observation and analysis, he will have a personal conclusion. As a result, this person forms his point of view in one way or another. Therefore, the content, nature, level of impact, benefit or harm to society, and the invitation to good or evil of any information have a positive or negative effect on the balance of the individual, society, and state. From this point of view, the role of ensuring informational and psychological security in the protection and development of national interests will increase even more. Around us, the development of science and technology and its impact on people is becoming stronger and superior to the impact of society and nature. The volume of information collected and created by mankind is expanding and is observed to increase every decade, but the number of human brain and the number of cells that make it up has not changed, moreover, the duration of education is increasing, and therefore the risk of informational stress increases. gives birth. The brain has a wide capacity to receive information, it is dangerous to increase the amount of information, but if there is a need to process a large amount of information in a short period of time, it causes a strong nervous tension and causes informational stress, that is, the amount of information entering the brain and the speed, which does not correspond to biological and social possibilities, also causes informational stress. Here, if the amount of information is one factor, and secondly, the lack of time and personal motivation are added to it by social reasons, the self-protection mechanism of the brain will stop working, and a person will not be able to protect himself from informational stress. Adolescents appear as the weakest impressionable group in such a situation. Information-psychological security is, first of all, to protect a person's psyche from destructive ideas that deprive him of his beliefs and convictions. Based on this, it can be said that the need for informational and psychological security is, first of all, directly related to man and society, man and state, individual and his inviolability, nation and national values, customs, traditions, historical and cultural heritage, generations. It is caused by the presence of destructive ideas and aggressive ideologies. In addition, if information and psychological security is not observed, if its effective measures are not taken, destructive ideas can undermine national security. In a densely informed society, the increasingly developing technologies of modern psychological influence through information have a strong influence on the formation of the thinking of individuals and society in one way or another.

Information society is a concept that describes the qualitative state of the human society, which is formed at the current stage of development and is based on the rational use of information and information technologies in all spheres of social life. The founders of the theory of the information society, looking at social development from the point of view of "change of stages", connect its formation with the emergence of the fourth economy, the "information sector", which emerged after the economy of agriculture, industry and services. According to them, capital and labor, which are the basis of industrial society, give way to information and knowledge in the information society. In order to ensure the safety of the information exchange process in the conditions of Uzbekistan, we think that in the conditions of information attacks, special attention should be paid to the following means: that is, coordination of the activities of information media, our national identity and interests through modern methods; use of all modern means against personal information security; use of new approaches in the coverage of domestic and foreign policy events; It would be appropriate to develop systematic approaches to the analysis of Uzbekistan's international relations, to pay special attention to the integration of the press and electronic media in the work of ensuring the information supply of the reforms, and to control the scope of all informational influences

References

- Abduazimov O. Mass media - a factor in building civil society. -Tashkent: Academy, 2008 98 p.
- Kenjaboyev A.T. Problems of formation of national information system. - Tashkent: IbnSino, 2004. - 252 p.
- Yaqubova M. Philosophical foundations of information technologies. /Methodological manual. Tashkent: Star - Polygraph. 2008
- Любимова В. Самоисцеление творчеством и адаптацией к жизни. Методы психологической самопомощи (Психологический практикум)/ Н.В. Любимова. – Ростов н/Д: Феникс, 2006. – 64 с.
- Научись отдыхать!: Техники релаксации / С.В. Баранова. – Ростов н/Д.: Феникс, 2008. – 156 с.
- Основы психической саморегуляции: Учебное пособие для студ. высш.учеб.заведений / Г.Р. Шагивалеева, В.Р. Бильданова. – Елабуга: Изд-во ЕГПУ, 2009. – 116 с.
- Разыкова, Л. Т., Игамова, И. С., Рахматова, Ф. Г., Муратова, Ш. Н., Мамадиярова, Д. У., & Кучкарова, О. О. (2019). Эффективность педагогического общения в подготовке врачей. Наука и образование сегодня, (11 (46)), 55-57.
- Разыкова, Л. Т., Игамова, И. С., & Муратова, Ш. Н. (2019). Роль психологической атмосферы семьи в становлении и развитии личности. Наука и образование сегодня, (11 (46)), 58-60.
- Tuychievna R. L., Tohirova F. Z. Mental processes the state of the human in their violation //Archive of Conferences. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 1. – С. 179-182.
- Tuychiyevna R. L. The content and conditions of the implementation of a person-centered approach in the educational process //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 1220-1224.
- Tuychiyevna R. L. COMMUNICATION AS A MEANS OF PEDAGOGICAL COOPERATION //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 374-377.
- Разыкова Л. Т. ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ЛИТЕРАТУРНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ //Наука, образование и культура. – 2022. – №. 2 (62). – С. 42-45.

Разыкова, Лола Туйчиевна. "ЭТИЧЕСКИЙ КЛИМАТ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ИЛИ (НЕЭТИЧНОЕ ПОВЕДЕНИЕ НА РАБОЧЕМ МЕСТЕ)." BOSHQARUV VA ETIKAQOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI 2.8 (2022): 54- 58.